

ECONOSCITECH INTEGRATION

ISSUE
6

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

American University
of Technology

Powered by Arizona State University®

ISSN: 3060-5075

Acceptance of articles
PUBLISHED MONTHLY

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ELECTRONIC JOURNAL
"ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION"
HAS BEEN REGISTERED UNDER
THE NUMBER C-5669651 BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND
MASS COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA)
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN,
EFFECTIVE FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

In accordance with Resolution No. 384/6 dated April 10, 2026, issued by the Presidium of the Supreme Attestation Commission under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this journal is included in the list of recommended international scientific publications for publishing the primary research findings of doctoral dissertations in the field of Economic Sciences.

Partners: Tashkent State University of Economics / American University of Technology in Tashkent (AUT)

Electronic publication, Issue 6. 374 pages.
Approved for publication on Iyun, 2026.

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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR IMPLEMENTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS.....	10
Shakirxodjayeva Zuxra Rustamxanovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT PROCESSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	16
Aliyeva Zilola Mamatvalyevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SECTORS IN TASHKENT CITY.....	23
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
GREEN BONDS VS. SUSTAINABILITYLINKED LOANS: WHICH WORKS FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONISATION?	29
Ataxanov Umidbek Olimovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬЮ БАНКА.....	34
Маликова Дилрабо Муминовна	
ECONOMETRIC MODELLING OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	42
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
AN INTEGRAL INDEX METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT POTENTIAL OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES	49
Sayyora Bakhtiyorovna Nazirova	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЕ, ПУБЛИЧНЫЕ И ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ГРАНИЦЫ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ.....	53
Срождиддинова Зарина Хайриддиновна	
BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FINANCIAL TRANSACTION MONITORING SYSTEM (SMART CONTRACTS, DECENTRALIZED DATABASE, AND AUDIT TRAILS).....	58
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	65
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF LABOR RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN SURXONDARYO REGION.....	72
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
ASSESSING THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH ACROSS THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN USING INTENSITY COEFFICIENTS AND CLUSTER ANALYSIS.....	77
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifkhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING AGRIVOLTAIC SYSTEMS IN UZBEKISTAN	85
Jabborov Shaymurod Akram o'g'li	
Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li	
Atoyeva Mohinur Amrilloevna	
Avazov Jonibek Azizbek o'g'li	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА НА ТРАЕКТОРИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	91
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
FINANCING GREEN PROJECTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS	97

Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna

FORMULA-BASED DISTRIBUTION OF INTERGOVERNMENTAL TRANSFERS TO LOCAL BUDGETS IN UZBEKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE SIMULATION ANALYSIS BASED ON 2026 FORECAST INDICATORS.....	103
Umidjon Pardaev	
Sarvar Maxmudov	
GOVERNMENT FUNDING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES: FINANCIAL PROMOTION MECHANISMS.....	115
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FORECASTING EXPORT AND IMPORT INDICATORS OF BUKHARA REGION	122
Ergashev Mirjon Yorqin o'g'li	
A CUSTOMER-ORIENTED INTEGRATIVE METHODOLOGICAL MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY	130
Bakayev Ziyovuddinkhan Toshbolta ogli	
A PESTLI ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM.....	139
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN	146
Khikmatullayeva Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi	
CHANGE MANAGEMENT DURING QUALITY ASSURANCE REFORM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	154
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
СТРАТЕГИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	162
Каримова Дилафруз Садриддин кизи	
E-COMMERCE AS A DIGITAL FORM OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES.....	167
Eshbayeva Shahnoza Fakhriddinovna	
ADVANTAGES OF IMPLEMENTING AN OCCUPATIONAL AND SKILLS MAPPING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN'S LABOUR MARKET	172
S.B.Goyipnazarov	
S.M.Kurbanbaeva	
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF FIXED ASSETS UTILIZATION IN RAILWAY ENTERPRISES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	178
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING RESOURCE USE IN THE CONTEXT OF A GREEN ECONOMY.....	183
Karimov Islombek Bekpolat o'g'li	
THE IMPACT OF ECOTOURISM ON REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	
Samiev Siroj Saitovich	
Ochilova Guli Rashid kizi	
THE IMPACT OF RISK ALLOCATION ON INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) PROJECTS	197
Khaydarova Charos Nizomiddinovna	
PROSPECTS FOR CHANGING THE VOLUME OF GRAPE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VITICULTURE COMPLEX.....	202
Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ	

И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ.....	209
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
ENHANCING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT INFLOWS IN THE POST-CRISIS ERA: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	215
Foziljon Rustamov Hazratkulovich	
CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	219
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
THE PECULIARITIES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL AREAS.....	225
Makhliso Umarova	
CHALLENGES OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN HUMAN CAPITAL AND STRATEGIES FOR THEIR RESOLUTION.....	231
Aloviddin Zayniddinov Zayniddin ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF SUCCESSFUL AGROTOURISM DESTINATIONS IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	237
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani o'g'li	
ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORT AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL.....	247
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	
ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF BUSINESS ENTITIES AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE FACTORS SHAPING IT: THE CASE OF BUKHARA REGION.....	254
Djurayeva Munira Sadillovovna	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE ECONOMY OF BUKHARA REGION AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT TRENDS: AN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES AND REGIONAL CONCENTRATION.....	261
Azizjon Anvarovich Kadirov	
Nigina Djurayevna Yusupova	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BORDER TRANSPORT SYSTEMS.....	268
Ikromov Elyor Ibdulloevich	
ПУТИ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ АУДИТОРСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	273
Бобонарова Камола	
GREEN BONDS AND SOVEREIGN DEBT INSTRUMENTS FOR INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET RENEWAL: AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS.....	278
Suleimanov Farrukh	
ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES.....	286
Qudratova Gulzoda Mahmudovna	
THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	291
Munisa Abdurakhmonova	
ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH BASED ON THE COBBDOUGLAS PRODUCTION FUNCTION: A CASE STUDY OF SURXONDARYA REGION.....	296
Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
GENERAL APPROACHES TO COST REDUCTION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	302
Kamola Saidova	

СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ВНУТРЕННЕГО АУДИТА В БЮДЖЕТНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ.....	307
Саитмуратов Саитмурат Машарип угли	
A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE IMPACT OF INTERMEDIATION SERVICES ON BANK PERFORMANCE AND ITS STATISTICAL RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	314
Miraxmedov Jasur Isroilovich	
EMPLOYER BRANDING IN UZBEKISTAN: HOW TO BECOME AN EMPLOYER OF CHOICE FOR TALENT	320
Doniyorova Fotimabonu Alisher qizi	
FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	325
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	331
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS OF MATERIAL COSTS IN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTITIES BASED ON MODERN MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS.....	336
Sa'dullayeva Sayyora Nasillo qizi	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC APPROACHES AND BARRIERS TO THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	341
Samieva Gulnoza Tokhirovna	
THE IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF LABOR POTENTIAL ON THE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF A REGION (A case study of the Khorezm region).....	348
Kutlimuratov Mansurbek Sattarovich	
CHARACTERISTICS OF CLUSTERING TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.....	354
Asadbek Eshniyozov	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	358
Abdullaev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	
THE ROLE OF 5G TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE OF TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES	366
Saidqosimova Umida Ibragimovna	
DIGITAL PLATFORMS AND THE EFFICIENCY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	371
Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTEREST RATE RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Seitnazarov Daniyar Bakhadyrovich	
METHODOLOGY AND WAYS OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	385
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
FOREIGN COUNTRIES' EXPERIENCE IN ORGANIZING AND MANAGING SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	391
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	

FOREIGN COUNTRIES' EXPERIENCE IN ORGANIZING AND MANAGING SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES

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Abstract. This article analyzes the experience of developed and developing countries in the organization and management of small industrial zones. In particular, it examines the institutional mechanisms of industrial zone management, methods of attracting investment, and their impact on regional development in China, South Korea, Turkey, Germany, and Singapore. Based on the results of the study, priority areas for the effective management of small industrial zones are identified, and practical recommendations applicable to the conditions of Uzbekistan are developed.

Keywords: small industrial zone, industrial policy, regional development, investment, management mechanism, cluster, industrialization, foreign experience.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada rivojlangan va rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda kichik sanoat zonalarini tashkil etish va boshqarish tajribasi tahlil qilingan. Xususan, Xitoy, Janubiy Koreya, Turkiya, Germaniya va Singapur misolida sanoat zonalarini boshqarishning institutsional mexanizmlari, investitsiyalarni jalb etish usullari hamda ularning hududiy rivojlanishga ta'siri o'rganilgan. Tadqiqot natijasida kichik sanoat zonalarini samarali boshqarishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari aniqlanib, O'zbekiston sharoitida qo'llash mumkin bo'lgan amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kichik sanoat zonasi, sanoat siyosati, hududiy rivojlanish, investitsiyalar, boshqaruv mexanizmi, klaster, sanoatlashtirish, xorijiy tajriba.

Аннотация. В данной статье проанализирован опыт развитых и развивающихся стран в области организации и управления малыми промышленными зонами. В частности, исследованы институциональные механизмы управления промышленными зонами, методы привлечения инвестиций и их влияние на региональное развитие на примере Китая, Южной Кореи, Турции, Германии и Сингапура. По результатам исследования определены приоритетные направления эффективного управления малыми промышленными зонами и разработаны практические рекомендации, применимые в условиях Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: малая промышленная зона, промышленная политика, региональное развитие, инвестиции, механизм управления, кластер, индустриализация, зарубежный опыт.

INTRODUCTION

In the global economy, small industrial zones are recognized as an important tool for developing industrial production, effectively utilizing the economic potential of regions, and attracting investment. Particularly in the context of economic transformation, industrial zones play an important role in supporting small businesses and private entrepreneurship, creating new jobs, and reducing interregional economic disparities.

In recent years, large-scale reforms have been implemented in many countries around the world to develop small industrial zones and industrial parks. In particular, the experience of China, South Korea, Singapore, and Turkey is of great importance in developing effective models for managing industrial zones.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is also paid to the development of small industrial zones as one of the key directions of industrialization policy. Therefore, studying the experience of foreign countries and adapting it to national practice is an urgent scientific and practical issue.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Modern scientific views on the management of industrial zones and the improvement of their competitiveness are reflected in Michael Porter's works *The Competitive Advantage of Nations* (1990) and *Clusters and the New Economics of Competition* (1998). Porter developed the cluster theory and scientifically substantiated that the close territorial concentration of enterprises accelerates innovation, reduces production costs, and increases investment attractiveness [1].

The report *Industrial Parks for Inclusive and Sustainable Industrial Development* (2019), published by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), analyzes the importance of industrial zones in sustainable economic development. The study highlights the role of industrial parks in promoting innovative development, technology transfer, and job creation.

UNIDO's report *Industrial Parks and Economic Transformation* (2021) examines the experiences of China, South Korea, Vietnam, and Singapore and concludes that the success of industrial zones depends on modern management systems, digitalization, and innovative infrastructure.

The OECD report *Industrial Policy for the Sustainable Development Goals* (2020) emphasizes the need to introduce green economy principles, environmental sustainability, and digital technologies into the management of industrial zones.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In conducting this study, several scientific methods of economic analysis were applied. The research employed statistical data analysis, comparative analysis, a systematic approach, logical generalization, and economic analysis methods. The impact of regional industrial zones on economic development was examined based on scientific sources and statistical data. In addition, international experience in the organization and management of industrial zones was analyzed within the framework of the study.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Chinese Experience. China is one of the most successful countries in the world in the development of industrial zones. The country has attracted large-scale investment through the creation of special economic zones and industrial parks. The management of industrial zones is carried out through cooperation between central and local authorities.

The main advantages of the Chinese experience include strong state support, modern infrastructure, export-oriented production, and the introduction of innovative technologies.

The first special economic zones in China were established in 1980, among which Shenzhen, Zhuhai, Shantou, and Xiamen were of particular importance. These zones provided investors with tax incentives, customs preferences, and simplified administrative procedures. As a result, large amounts of foreign investment were attracted within a short period, and industrial production increased significantly.

One of the important aspects of the Chinese experience is the active participation of the state in the development of industrial zones. While the central government creates the legal framework for the establishment of industrial zones, local authorities carry out the tasks of infrastructure construction, investor attraction, and coordination of enterprise activities. Such a two-tier management system contributes to the effective functioning of industrial zones [2].

In China, the management of industrial zones is organized according to the "one-stop shop" principle. Investors can receive land allocation, construction permits, registration, and other services through a single center. This reduces administrative barriers and significantly lowers the cost of doing business. Another important feature of Chinese industrial zones is their development based on the principle of clustering. Each industrial zone specializes in a specific industry or direction. For example, specialized clusters have been created for electronics, automotive manufacturing, chemistry, information technology, and mechanical engineering. This has enabled the development of cooperative relations between enterprises, the reduction of logistics costs, and the acceleration of innovation exchange.

South Korean Experience. In South Korea, industrial zones are developed according to the principle of industrial clustering. Close cooperation has been established between enterprises, research centers, and universities. As a result, the production and export of innovative products have increased significantly.

The policy of supporting small and medium-sized businesses in South Korea is also closely linked to industrial zones. Small enterprises are integrated into large industrial clusters and become an important link in the supply chain. This contributes to increasing production efficiency and strengthening the value chain.

Developed transport and logistics infrastructure is also one of the important advantages of South Korean industrial zones. Industrial zones are integrated with seaports, railways, and highways, which allows export operations to be carried out quickly and efficiently.

Ha-Joon Chang, who studied the South Korean experience, emphasizes that the success of industrial policy is based on strategic state intervention and long-term planning. In his view, industrial zones enabled the country to overcome technological backwardness and become a high-income economy.

Research shows that the success of South Korean industrial zones is determined by the following factors: strategic industrial policy of the state, integration of science and industry, high-tech production, cooperation between large corporations and small businesses, developed logistics and export infrastructure, an innovative ecosystem, and investment in research and development.

In conclusion, the South Korean experience shows that small industrial zones can be formed not only as production areas, but also as centers of innovative development. This experience has important practical significance for Uzbekistan in modernizing industrial zones, developing innovative clusters, and introducing elements of the digital economy [3].

German Experience. In Germany, industrial zones are aimed at supporting small and medium-sized businesses. Engineering services, logistics centers, and business incubators operate in regional industrial parks. Public-private partnership mechanisms are widely used in this process.

The concept of industrial zone development in Germany has historically been closely linked to the principles of the regional economy and the social market economy. In particular, the system of small and medium-sized enterprises, known as the “Mittelstand,” is the main foundation of industrial zones. These enterprises are located in industrial zones and have become an important link in large production chains.

One of the main principles of managing industrial zones in Germany is the implementation of regional economic policy based on a federal structure. Each federal state (Bundesland) independently develops its own industrial policy and actively participates in the development of industrial zones. This system serves to reduce economic disparities between regions.

The mechanism of public-private partnership (PPP) is widely used in the development of industrial zones. While the state develops infrastructure, the private sector carries out production and innovation activities. This helps to use resources efficiently and reduce investment risks.

Another important feature of German industrial zones is their high level of specialization. For example, automotive and mechanical engineering clusters are developed in Baden-Württemberg, while electronics and aerospace industries are concentrated in Bavaria. This specialization increases production efficiency and strengthens global competitiveness.

In industrial zones, science and production are highly integrated. Universities, research centers, and technology parks work closely with industrial enterprises. For example, the Fraunhofer Society plays an important role in the development of applied research and industrial innovation in Germany. This organization, in cooperation with industrial enterprises, develops new technologies and introduces them into production.

Logistics and transport infrastructure are among the main advantages of German industrial zones. The country is located in the center of Europe, and its developed highways, railway networks, and river transport ensure the effective operation of industrial zones. In particular, the ports of Hamburg and Bremen play an important role in export operations.

Michael Porter, who studied the German experience, substantiated the relationship between territorial specialization and competitiveness in cluster theory, and German industrial zones are considered a practical expression of this theory [4].

The analysis shows that German industrial zones have achieved success due to the following main factors: a strong federal and regional management system, an economy based on small and medium-sized businesses, high specialization and clustering, integration of science and production, public-private partnership mechanisms, principles of environmental sustainability and “green industry,” and developed logistics infrastructure.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

First, the experience of foreign countries confirms that small industrial zones are an effective tool for regional economic development.

Second, the success of industrial zones depends on developed infrastructure, a favorable investment environment, and an effective management system.

Third, the introduction of innovative technologies and digital management mechanisms is an important factor in increasing the efficiency of industrial zones.

Based on the study, the following recommendations were developed:

Introduce digital management platforms in small industrial zones.

Develop industrial clusters and cooperative relations between enterprises.

Expand public-private partnership mechanisms.

Support innovative and export-oriented projects.

Introduce a comprehensive system of indicators for assessing the efficiency of industrial zones.

The practical implementation of these recommendations will help increase the competitiveness of small industrial zones in Uzbekistan, expand investment volumes, and accelerate regional economic development.

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Proofreader: Xondamir Ismoilov
Layout and Designer: Hasan Maqsudov

2026. № 6

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